

Received : 10 January 2024, Accepted: 15 April 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33282/rr.vx9i2.100>

How Does Corruption Hit the Good Governance in South Asia

Hafsa Gul¹, Misbah Zia¹, Waqas Anwar¹, Muhammad Rizwan², Saad Jaffer³, Imran Naseem⁴

Abstract

In South Asian nations, corruption continues to be a major obstacle to effective governance. In the context of South Asian countries, this study examines the effects of corruption on several aspects of governance, such as efficacy, the rule of law, the caliber of regulations, political stability, and accountability. Data from a thorough evaluation of governance indicators are studied using regression analysis and correlational approaches to determine the links between governance factors and corruption. The results show that in South Asian nations, corruption seriously compromises a number of dimensions of good administration. In particular, corruption shows detrimental impacts on political stability, the rule of law, the quality of regulations, and the management of corruption itself. On the other hand, elements like efficacy and the rule of law become important variables in the fight against corruption and the advancement of good governance. Nonetheless, the effect of accountability on corruption seems to be less significant, indicating the necessity for additional research into the mechanisms underlying it within the framework of governance. These findings highlight the critical need to combat corruption as a primary barrier to establishing effective governance in South Asian countries. To effectively address corruption, policymakers and stakeholders need to give priority to activities aimed at fostering accountability mechanisms, strengthening legal frameworks, and improving transparency. South Asian nations can set the path for better governance procedures, sustainable development, and fair socioeconomic progress in the area by taking a holistic approach to combating corruption.

KEYWORDS: Corruption, Good governance, Rule of Law, South Asian Countries

Introduction

Corruption is a global fact. It is not something new. Corruption existed in several forms since ancient times. Ancient Civilizations clearly shows corruption a significant

1. M.Phil. Scholar(Pakistan Studies), Department of Pakistan Studies, Abbottabad University of Science & Technology, Abbottabad, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Email: gulhafsa771@gmail.com

2 Associate Professor, Chairman Department of Pakistan Studies, Abbottabad University of Science & Technology, Abbottabad, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Email: rizwan@aust.edu.pk

3 Lecturer, Department of Pakistan Studies, Abbottabad University of Science & Technology, Abbottabad, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Email: saadjaffar@aust.edu.pk

4 **Corresponding Author** Assistant Professor, Department of Pakistan Studies, Abbottabad University of Science & Technology, Abbottabad, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Email: drimran.naseem@aust.edu.pk, dr.imrannaseem@gmail.com, URD Research Center, University of Religions and Denominations, Qom, Iran

problem among the Jews, the Chinese, the Japanese, the Greeks, the Romans, and the Aztecs of the New World (Thakur, 1979). In ancient Indian Continent large-scale corruption influenced public lives (Thakur, 1979). Corruption was obvious during British rule in India, there were almost systematic corruption at different levels of Political and Administrative institutions (Muhabbat,1999). Corruption is also a significant social, economic, legal and political concept entangled in ambiguity and consequently promoting disputes in the context of World efforts to bring down its dominance on public life. But this is not easy in any way. “Corruption is social, economic, legal and political concept entangled in ambiguity and consequently promoting disputes.”. According to World Bank, simplest definition of corruption is that “It is misuse of public power for private benefits (JAVAID, 2010). Governance is the framework for managing an organization and the procedure for holding its members accountable. Good Governance is the process by which government institutions ensure the welfare and fundamental rights of people, and works without corruption under rule of law. This article aims to analyze the impact of Corruption on Good Governance in South Asian countries, so here we discuss corruption and its impacts on governance in these countries;

British rule is largely responsible for Pakistan's corruption, as they bestowed titles and lands on their corrupt subjects (Awan, 2004). Subsequently, in the 1950s and 1960s, there were patronage schemes involving bonus vouchers and route permits, which facilitated additional corruption. The 1970 Nationalization Policy increased the opportunities for corruption for many government officials. There was evidence of corruption in business and religious circles during the 1980s. Transparency International Pakistan conducted a survey in 2004 and found the following causes of corruption in Pakistan: Low Salaries (16.54%), Discretionary Power (12.61%), Monopoly of Power (16.43%), Lack of Accountability (31.68%), Red tape (4.28%), the Power of Influential People (4.59%), and Others (4.9%). Whatever the causes of this widespread corruption trend, it is still a fact that it has had a significant impact on the nation's economy, society, and society at large. Here are some key areas it affects that are discussed: According to Sala-i-Martin and Porter (2008), corruption is the third biggest concern for business corporations in Pakistan, behind inadequate infrastructure and government management, in the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Report (2008). This directly threatens the Direct Foreign Investment (DFI) system, which is sorely required to maintain the diminishing foreign exchange reserves, promote economic growth, and create jobs. In reality, the show is about ruthless, unchecked corruption in the collection of taxes, customs, levies, WAPDA dues, expensive purchases made by the public sector, and incompetent key public sector organizations such as the PIA, the railway, the steel mill, and others result in significant annual capital creation and expense deficits for the government, which prompts the government to borrow money from the IMF and other foreign and private sources. This increased debt repayment widens the deficit and forces the government to raise the price of utilities like gas, electricity, CNG, and petroleum. That requires the Pakistani people to make a sizable payment. Corruption, when it occurs, has a direct and significant impact on the lives of common people, even when it occurs in distant and higher places. Years of development efforts have been derailed in the nation due to widespread fraud on nearly every task and massive consumption of advancement funds. The unchecked spread of

corruption has also left an impression on the nation's unequal professional morality. The order of the day is black marketing, hoarding, deceiving the manager, accumulation, and accumulation. Individual businessmen, companies, business groups, and occasionally an entire industry are found involved in these wrongdoings. Furthermore, the nation loses its way when corruption affects the way the judiciary, which occupies the last position, is organized. The whole financial system is impacted by the lack of an equitable legal system, as private and foreign investments are avoided out of concern for annexation and expropriation. In summary, the nation's unchecked corruption has severely impacted every industry, and the community as a whole has put up with substantial disruptions to the social structure and workplace (Xu, 2014).

Many analysts argue that a large portion of India's current corruption stems from its colonial past. Under the British Raj, which divided the country into districts with commissioner-controlled province administrations beginning in 1858, Indian citizens were kept out of politics. Public employees were forbidden by the Official Secrets Act of 1923 from disclosing state secrets to the general public, ostensibly to protect military and intelligence secrets from the government. After India gained independence in 1947, the new government enacted strict economic regulations designed to grow local markets. The 1951 Industries Act, for instance, required all new industrial processes to obtain a license from the national authority. The rules discouraged foreign investment, stifled competition, and normalized bribery as a standard business practice.

The government's overbearing control over the economy led to the nickname "License Raj" for the years leading up to 1991. Large sums of public funds were diverted by widespread corruption which frequently hurt the poorest people meant for social welfare, aid, and public works projects. "Historically, the roots of India's corruption came from the proliferation of licenses," stated the former CFR. Jagdish Bhagwati is a Senior Fellow for international Economics. The goal was to guarantee economical utilization of resources, so you wouldn't squander foreign currency. This is what Indians have been up until this point extremely conscious of the fact that the system of licenses and permits was the cause of corruption on an enormous scope (Tahiliani, 2002). India ranks 71st out of 102 countries in 2002 and has a score of just 2.7 out of 10, making it one of the most corrupt countries in the world. India received a lower score in 2002 (2.7) than in 1999 (2.9). India is ranked lower than China in TI's survey of perceptions among international business. India is listed in the World Competitiveness Year Book 2000 as one of the nations where there is a lot of corruption and bribery (Biswas, 2012).

It appears that political corruption, starting with electoral corruption, is the root cause of corruption in public office. Who governs over more than 120 crore Indians is decided by the general election. In their pursuit of power, political parties have spent millions of rupees on the Lok Sabha election, but none of them has ever been held accountable for the majority of the money spent on the process. No one reveals where the money comes from. Both an audit and proper accounts are absent. Nobody knows where the money comes from. The high expense of campaigning and dubious tactics used by political parties appears to have contributed to an increase in electoral corruption in India in recent years. The lack of appropriate oversight and

regulation of the costs incurred by political parties and candidates has led to a general critique that there has been insufficient oversight of the rise in electoral corruption over time.

The report states that the Lok Sabha election is expected to cost close to Rs. 1100 crores. Comparably, it was estimated that the 2004 Lok Sabha elections cost approximately Rs. 1093.06 crores to hold. The political parties spend more and more of this public money on general elections; however, they are not held responsible for it. There are still significant resource shortages in rural India in regards to housing, infrastructure, drinking water, health, education, and sanitation. Both the NREGS and the Indira Awas Yojana are corrupt. According to Mr. Mohit Sen, a member of the Planning Commission, the Rural Employment Guarantee program has little room for growth. India's rural development is anchored by the Panchayati Raj Institution. The Panchayati Raj Institution is an establishment that has enhanced widespread involvement in the process of development and empowered the rural populace. In rural India, all state and federally sponsored programs are carried out by the Panchayati Raj Institution. However, because Panchayat officials are corrupt, the benefits of all programs do not reach the real beneficiaries in rural India, and people are not motivated to take part in development projects (Gupta, 2023). India ranks 80 out of 180 countries in the Transparency International Corruption Perception Index for 2022, with a score of 40. (Corruption perception index, 2022) Corruption leads to inefficiencies in the healthcare sector. It causes medicine to be duplicated and creates disparities in access to admission, doctor consultations, and diagnostic services(R&T, 2018). The Indian public services have been rocked by a number of significant scandals involving high-ranking public officials in recent years. This scandal implies that the political and bureaucratic structures in India are now rife with corruption.

According to the Sri Lanka Governance Report 1 (2010, 2011, 2012–2013), corruption is a major issue in Sri Lanka. It has led to resignations as well as the mobilization of the populace and movements against dishonest political figures. Prior scholarly investigations concerning corruption in Sri Lanka have predominantly examined the correlation between corruption and social phenomena, including but not limited to development assistance and ethnic conflict (Goodhand and Klem, 2005; Lindberg and Orjuela, 2011), the financial consequences of war (Arunatilake, Jayasuriya, and Kelegama, 2001), avarice and complaints (Korf, 2005), the aftermath of the tsunami (Perera-Mubarak 2012), and the assessment of corruption (Herath, 2010). In Sri Lanka, the political and administrative spheres of the government are rife with corruption. Almost all processes involved in providing public services—such as getting a driver's license, contract awards, procurements, and payments for goods and services supplied—are impacted by corruption to varying degrees (ADB, 2004). The Financial Times (FT), a Sri Lankan newspaper, revealed on February 9, 2017, that 15 public institutions had lost 110 billion rupees in 2015 and 2016 The article characterizes these institutions as "wasteful and uneconomic state enterprises (Mahmood, 2010)." Here we discuss impacts of corruption on governance in Sri Lanka: One of the biggest challenges to Sri Lanka's efforts to achieve good governance, sustainable development, and citizen well-being is corruption. One of the most notable effects of corruption on good governance in Sri Lanka is its influence over political processes. Corruption

distorts political decision-making because it grants individuals in wealthy and powerful positions undue influence over laws and regulations. This leads to a lack of accountability, transparency, and justice in governance since the corrupt usually take precedence over the public interest when making decisions. In Sri Lanka, corruption impedes the efficient provision of public services. The availability and caliber of vital services like infrastructure, healthcare, and education are jeopardized when bribery and favoritism control how opportunities and resources are distributed. Due to the disproportionate impact on the weakest members of society, this impedes social advancement and sustains inequality. Furthermore, dishonest behavior in public office undermines good governance by eroding public confidence in the government's capacity to meet the needs of its constituents. The widespread corruption in Sri Lanka poses a threat to the administration of justice and the rule of law. Corrupt influences have the ability to undermine legal systems and law enforcement organizations, giving the wealthy and well-connected carte blanche. As a result, there is a continued culture of impunity where the powerful and wealthy can avoid taking responsibility for their deeds, further undermining public confidence in the legal system. The prospects for good governance are further diminished by the deterioration of the rule of law, which challenges the core values of justice and equality. In Sri Lanka, corruption also has a significant social impact. It normalizes unethical behavior and fosters a culture of dishonesty, normalizing corrupt practices in society. As a result of losing faith in the honesty of their institutions and fellow citizens, people may become less cohesive and trustworthy in society. Furthermore, the unequal distribution of resources brought about by corruption hinders inclusive development and exacerbates social inequality. In the end, corruption weakens Sri Lankan society's social cohesion and reduces the likelihood of a just and equitable society.

In Bangladesh, corruption is not a recent development. The East India Company, which essentially took over Bengal in 1757, maintained an extremely corrupt system by paying its workers' wages below subsistence levels, forcing them to turn to extortion and private enterprise. "A set of men whose sense of honor and duty to their employers had been estranged by the larger pursuit of their own immediate advantages," was how Robert Clive put the company's staff. , Bangladesh's leaders have frequently denounced the high rate of corruption since the country's independence, but neither government has been able to effectively address the systemic problems that allow corruption to thrive, even after democracy was restored in the 1990s. Many would contend that the business community has profited from it while still putting up with it. Unfortunately, the majority of the cost has fallen on tax payers and regular people, particularly the impoverished. The World Bank calculates that corruption costs the economy between two and three percent of GDP growth annually.

If corruption was curbed by the government, per capita income might double (Transparency International, 2009). Transparency International reports that Bangladesh has moved up in the much-discussed global corruption perception index, rising to 13th place, down from 10th in 2008, despite widespread perceptions of political and administrative corruption. (Bangladeshi media, 2009). The practice of providing bribes in return for healthcare and education is merely an indication of the violation of basic human rights. Corruption in local government, income tax,

vat and customs, land administration, judiciary, law enforcement, and politics poses a serious threat to human rights in Bangladesh. The 2010 TIB Household Survey found that bribery was demanded by 71.9% of households that dealt with different public and private service sectors to obtain services. Bribery was paid by 68.1% of the households dealing with law enforcement, followed by the judiciary at 59.6% and land administration at 67%. Income tax, vat, customs, agricultural sector, and 43.9%, 38.1%, and 36.7% of the households receiving services from local government were required to pay bribes, correspondingly (TIB, 2010). Education is one of the best ways to improve people's quality of life (Aardt, 2008; TIB, 2010). Unfortunately, corruption has an impact on Bangladesh's educational system as well. The ubiquity of corruption makes it difficult to ensure that this field receives high-quality education. Students had to deal with corruption and irregularities in order to get free books, receive stipends, and be admitted (TIB, 2010). Of the students from the households surveyed, 74.6% of them paid an average of Tk. 90.72 as a bribe to secure the scholarship, and 22% of them experienced irregularities with their Upobritti (sub-scholarships) (TIB, 2008). Because poor and rural people do not have the same access to health care as wealthy and urban people, health services in Bangladesh are provided in an unequal manner by both the public and private sectors. Furthermore, the public health sector, where impoverished and rural individuals typically seek services, is hindered in its efforts to experience sustained growth by the existence of corruption. Common practices in the public health sector include neglect of duty, doctors practicing privately during business hours, hospital staff selling drugs at lower prices in the marketplace (pharmacies/drug shops), accepting payments for services that people are entitled to receive free of charge, and paying unofficial fees in the form of bribes and payments to obtain services that individuals are entitled to receive at no cost are standard procedures in Bangladesh's public health sector (Jahan and Solehan, 2006). In government hospitals, irregularities and corruption were experienced by 38.4% of households receiving care from Upazila Health Complex; this was followed by general hospitals (35.2%) and medical college hospitals (33.6%) (TIB, 2010). The most significant industry in Bangladesh is agriculture, which employs half of the labor force and generates 21% of the nation's GDP (Gross Domestic Product). Food security, sustainable development, and the reduction of poverty all greatly depend on agricultural development (The 2008 Agriculture Census, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics). However, the presence of corruption in this industry hinders its intended growth. According to TIB (2010), 95% of the households that experienced irregularities and corruption in the fertilizer delivery process were required to pay an average of Tk. 314 extra, and 85.9% of the households did not receive the fertilizer on time.

In Nepal, the issue of corruption has dominated the political agenda for at least ten years and even more so in recent years. It is acknowledged as a major contributing factor to Nepal's underdevelopment. It is practiced at all societal levels, is very common, and takes many forms. Politicians, businesspeople, and bureaucracy in Nepal are all deeply impacted by and intricately linked to corruption. According to Upadhyaya (2003), this presents a significant challenge to the modern Nepali

campaign. This is the fault of politicians, businesspeople, government employees, so-called academicians, and even customers.

Along with the rise in corruption, there is a decline in the quality of good governance (Panday, 2018). Numerous studies (Dahal et al., 2000; Bajracharya et al., 2019) demonstrate that the main causes of Nepal's underdevelopment are the country's high level of corruption and persistently poor governance. Transparency International Nepal's (2015) study demonstrates how poor Nepal's current state of governance is. Service recipients pay extra and illegal money to receive government services, according to the study. In a similar vein, people encountered corruption and paid bribes to obtain services from every government office, per a different study conducted by Transparency International Nepal (TI Nepal, 2016). Corruption has been flourishing in every sector in Nepal such as import, export, public expenditure, procurement process, service delivery, development activities, and project implementation process among others (TI, 2013). Dhungel (2018) argues that it is very difficult to find any sector, government agency and government personnel who are not involved in corrupt behavior. According to TI (2013), corruption has thrived chronically and structurally in Nepal across dominated bureaucracy, the politics, executive organ, judiciary, legislative, NGOs as well as donors and private sector. According to the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) published annually by Transparency International, Nepal is listed among the most corrupt countries in the world. That is why good governance is hampered by corruption in Nepal (Ghimire, 2023). This article aims to analyze the impacts of corruption on good governance in South Asian countries, examining its influence on different sectors of region, and to suggest the measures to overcome corruption.

Review of Literature: During review of literature, a lot of information regarding impact of corruption in South Asian countries is found, however, this research article will mainly focus on the impacts over good governance as a result of corruption.

In their article "Corruption and Governance in South Asia: Comparative Perspectives," Khan and Jameel (2017) examine the connection between corruption and governance within the framework of South Asian nations. They contend that corruption erodes public trust, impairs the efficiency of the economy, and weakens the efficacy of government institutions. The authors stress that in order to enhance governance in the area, extensive anti-corruption initiatives and institutional reforms are required. Choudhury and Sharmeen (2015), in their article "Corruption and Good Governance in South Asia." examined the intricate relationship between corruption and governance, emphasizing how corruption undermines institutional legitimacy, public confidence, and the rule of law in South Asia. The writers highlight the difficulties in eradicating corruption in South Asian nations and stress the necessity of institutional strength and political will in order to advance good governance. In their paper "Corruption and Its Impact on Good Governance in South Asia," Hasan and Mollah (2018) look into how corruption affects accountability, transparency, and the effectiveness of public institutions of South Asia, among other aspects of governance. They highlight how widespread corruption is in the area and how detrimental it is to social welfare and economic growth. The authors support coordinated efforts to improve good

governance in South Asian nations by addressing corruption through institutional and legislative reforms.

An important World Bank working paper titled "Corruption and the Provision of Health Care and Education Services" by Gupta, Davoodi, and Tiongson (2002) offers empirical evidence of the negative effects of corruption on the provision of basic public services, like healthcare and education, in South Asian nations. The writers emphasize that in order to increase social welfare and service delivery, governance reforms and anti-corruption measures are necessary. Khan (2010) examines the complex interrelationships between entrenched interests, power structures, and governance outcomes in South Asian nations in his book "Political Settlements and the Governance of Growth-Enhancing Institutions". The analysis provided by the author clarifies the ways in which corruption can impair the efficiency of institutions of governance and prevent the institutionalization of accountable and transparent governance systems. Jain, A. K. (2018). In his article "Corruption: A South Asian Perspective." offers a critical examination of corruption in the South Asian context, examining its effects on democratic institutions and governance. He emphasizes the difficulties that corruption presents to attaining good governance in the area by highlighting the connections between corruption and political stability, public sector effectiveness, and citizen participation. Hasan, Z (2020). In his article "Corruption and Its Implications for Good Governance in South Asia." highlights the problems that corrupt practices in South Asian public and private sectors present for good governance by examining the effects of corruption on governance. In order to effectively combat corruption, the paper provides empirical insights into how corruption affects important governance metrics and highlights the necessity of comprehensive governance reforms. Malhotra. P (2017). In his article "The Nexus Between Corruption and Good Governance in South Asia." examines the inter relationship between good governance and corruption, considering at how corruption affects the standard of public policies, governance institutions, and service delivery in South Asian countries. The author emphasizes the necessity of implementing focused anti-corruption initiatives to improve regional governance. Basu, K (2015). Article "The Costs of Corruption." In this article, Basu view at the social and economic value of corruption, emphasizing how bad it is for South Asian governance. He talks about how corruption taints the provision of public services, threatens the rule of law, and erodes public confidence in institutions, all of which make it more difficult for governments to support inclusive development and good governance in South Asia.

Corruption is a ubiquitous and harmful phenomenon that continues to impede socio-economic development and undermine the efficacy of public institutions in governance structures throughout South Asian nations. Even though a lot of research has shown how bad corruption is, a thorough quantitative analysis is still required to fully grasp the complex relationship between corruption and good governance in South Asia. The investigation of the complex relationship between corruption and good governance in South Asian nations from 2000 to onwards is the main goal of this quantitative research paper. This quantitative study is important because it helps to understand the complex relationship that exists in South Asian nations between corruption and good governance. The study attempts to provide empirical evidence that can guide policy

decisions by utilizing statistical methods to evaluate the impact. Creating strategies that effectively combat corruption and improve transparency requires an understanding of how corruption affects governance metrics. The governance issues that South Asian nations are facing, such as corruption, have a significant impact on the stability and development of the region. By concentrating on this area, the study can help advance knowledge of governance concerns in a framework that applies to the participating nations as well as to other areas dealing with comparable problems.

Our research questions are How does the level of corruption correlate with key indicators of good governance, such as transparency, accountability, and rule of law, in South Asian countries from 2000 onwards? How does the level of corruption in South Asian countries influence the effectiveness of public service delivery and administrative efficiency in the context of good governance? Why do certain political and economic reforms fail in addressing corruption and fostering good governance in South Asian nations? How has corruption impacted the trust of citizens in government institutions and their perception of the legitimacy of political processes in South Asian countries?

The paper aims to conduct an empirical analysis and quantitative measurement of the correlation between different measures of good governance, including rule of law, accountability, transparency, and the efficiency of public institutions, and corruption in South Asian nations. The sub objectives are 1) to assess the quantitative extent of corruption in South Asian countries from 2000 onwards through comprehensive data analysis. 2) To assess the extent to which corruption affects the quality of governance in South Asian countries, using quantitative data and statistical analysis to measure the magnitude and significance of this impact. 3) To examine the socioeconomic, political, and institutional factors that contributes to or mitigates the impact of corruption on good governance in South Asian countries, using rigorous quantitative analysis to identify significant variables and their relationships.

Sources and Methodology

The Methodology for this study is mainly based on quantitative form of research to describe and critically evaluate the impacts of Corruption on Good Governance in South Asian countries. This research is exploratory based on secondary sources. For this research statistical data is collected from the World Bank. To examine relationship between one dependent variable and one or more independent variables (e.g., Effectiveness, Rule of Law, Regulatory Quality, Political Stability, Control of Corruption, or Accountability) we conducted regression analysis by using provided data of South Asian countries. The results imply that corruption negatively impacts several facets of effective governance in South Asian nations. One of the most important ways to fight corruption and promote good governance in the world is to strengthen rules of law, regulatory frameworks, accountability systems, and institutions. Taken help from Artificial Intelligence (AI) for improved English grammar.

Regression Analysis:

To examine relationship between one dependent variable and one or more independent variables (e.g., Effectiveness, Rule of Law, Regulatory Quality, Political Stability, Control of Corruption, or Accountability) we conducted regression analysis by using provided data of South Asian countries. By using regression analysis we are able to understand nature and strength of relationships between variables.

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Effectiveness	-.4370	.61298	176
Rule Of Law	-.4831	.64276	176
Regulatory Quality	-.6339	.47876	176
Political Stability	-.9603	1.15491	176
Control Of Corruption	-.5335	.73418	176
Accountability	-.5060	.52145	176

- This statistics show negative mean value for all variables indicating average perceptions of these indicators. Negative numbers imply a gloomier outlook or a worse degree of efficacy, political stability, and regulatory excellence, rule of law, accountability, and corruption control.
- The dispersion or spread of the data points around the mean is measured by the standard deviations. Greater variety in answers or perceptions throughout the sample is indicated by higher standard deviations.
- The data indicates that opinions of political stability vary greatly across respondents and are generally lower when compared to other characteristics. Political stability has the lowest mean value (-0.9603) and the biggest standard deviation (1.15491).
- Regulatory quality has the lowest standard deviation (0.47876), and lowest mean value (-0.6339), suggesting relatively less variability in perceptions of regulatory quality among the respondents and suggesting that out of all the factors tested, it is thought to be the least important.
- Accountability has the highest mean value (-0.5060) among the factors measured, suggesting that it is perceived relatively more positively compared to other factors.

Correlations							
		Effective ness	Rule Of Law	Regulatory Quality	Political Stability	Control Of Corruption	Accountab ility
Pearson Correlation	Effectiveness	1.000	.902	.703	.790	.814	.508
	Rule Of Law	.902	1.000	.719	.755	.846	.665
	Regulatory Quality	.703	.719	1.000	.495	.428	.438
	Political Stability	.790	.755	.495	1.000	.785	.354
	Control Of Corruption	.814	.846	.428	.785	1.000	.408

	Accountability	.508	.665	.438	.354	.408	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Effectiveness	.	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	Rule Of Law	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Regulatory Quality	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	Political Stability	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	Control Of Corruption	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	Accountability	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	Effectiveness	176	176	176	176	176	176
	Rule Of Law	176	176	176	176	176	176
	Regulatory Quality	176	176	176	176	176	176
	Political Stability	176	176	176	176	176	176
	Control Of Corruption	176	176	176	176	176	176
	Accountability	176	176	176	176	176	176

The provided correlation matrix shows the Pearson correlation coefficients between different variables related to governance indicators, along with their associated p-values and sample sizes (N). Let's analyze and interpret this data:

Degree of Correlation Strength:

A complete positive correlation is denoted by a correlation coefficient of 1, a perfect negative correlation by a correlation coefficient of -1 and no correlation is shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.

The coefficients of weaker correlations are closer to 0, whereas those with strong correlations are closer to 1 or -1.

Interpretations:

Effectiveness:

- Strong positive correlations (above 0.7) with Rule of Law (0.902), Regulatory Quality (0.703), Political Stability (0.790), and Control of Corruption (0.814).
- Moderate positive correlation with Accountability (0.508).

Rule of Law:

- Strong positive correlations with Effectiveness (0.902), Control of Corruption (0.846), and Accountability (0.665).
- Moderate positive correlations with Regulatory Quality (0.719) and Political Stability (0.755).

Regulatory Quality:

- Moderate positive correlations with Rule of Law (0.719) and Political Stability (0.495).
- Weak positive correlations with Effectiveness (0.703) and Control of Corruption (0.428).

Political Stability:

- Strong positive correlations with Effectiveness (0.790) and Control of Corruption (0.785).
- Moderate positive correlations with Rule of Law (0.755).
- Weak positive correlation with Regulatory Quality (0.495).

Control of Corruption:

- Strong positive correlations with Effectiveness (0.814), Rule of Law (0.846), and Political Stability (0.785).
- Weak positive correlation with Regulatory Quality (0.428).

Accountability:

- Moderate positive correlations with Rule of Law (0.665) and Control of Corruption (0.408).
- Weak positive correlations with Effectiveness (0.508) and Regulatory Quality (0.438).

Significance:

- All correlations have p-values less than 0.001, indicating that they are statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level.

According to the statistics, there appears to be a substantial correlation between governance metrics in South Asian countries, including Rule of Law, Political Stability, Effectiveness, and Control of Corruption.

These results suggest the interconnectedness of governance systems by suggesting that advancements in one area of governance frequently coincide with advancements in other areas.

Coefficients ^a											
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
		1	(Constant)	.097			.040		2.387	.018	
	Rule Of Law	.484	.103	.507	4.704	<.001	.902	.339	.135	.071	14.105
	Regulatory Quality	.243	.064	.190	3.778	<.001	.703	.278	.108	.326	3.065
	Political Stability	.106	.026	.199	4.059	<.001	.790	.297	.117	.343	2.918
	Control Of Corruption	.141	.062	.169	2.263	.025	.814	.171	.065	.148	6.750
	Accountability	-.061	.052	-.052	-1.169	.244	.508	-.089	-.034	.417	2.399

a. Dependent Variable: Effectiveness

When all other factors are held constant, the standardized coefficients (Beta) show the relative significance of each independent variable in predicting the dependent variable. A summary of the analysis and interpretation is provided below:

Rule of Law:

The coefficient (B) is 0.484, meaning that, while leaving other variables fixed, the Effectiveness should rise by 0.484 units for every unit increase in Rule of Law. Rule of Law appears to be a major predictor of effectiveness, as indicated by the highly significant $(p < 0.001)$ t-value (4.704). Of the variables included, Rule of Law appears to have the largest influence on Effectiveness, as indicated by the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.507.

Regulatory Quality:

The coefficient (B) is 0.243, meaning that, while holding other variables constant, the Effectiveness is predicted to rise by 0.243 units for every unit increase in Regulatory Quality. Regulatory Quality is a major predictor of Effectiveness, as shown by the very significant $(p < 0.001)$ t-value (3.778).

When compared to other variables, the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.190 indicates that Regulatory Quality has a moderate effect on Effectiveness.

Political stability:

With all other variables held constant, the coefficient (B) of 0.106 indicates that, for every unit rise in Political Stability, there should be a corresponding 0.106 unit gain in Effectiveness. Political stability appears to be a strong predictor of effectiveness, as indicated by the very significant $(p < 0.001)$ t-value (4.059). Effectiveness is reportedly moderately impacted by Political Stability, according to the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.199.

Control of Corruption:

The coefficient (B) is 0.141, meaning that, while holding other variables fixed, the Effectiveness should rise by 0.141 units for every unit increase in Control of Corruption. Control of Corruption is a significant predictor of effectiveness, albeit to a lower extent than other variables, according to the significant t-value (2.263) $(p = 0.025)$. In comparison to other factors, Control of Corruption appears to have a relatively smaller impact on Effectiveness, as indicated by the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.169.

Accountability:

The coefficient (B) is -0.061, meaning that, while maintaining other variables constant, the Effectiveness should fall by 0.061 units for every unit rise in Accountability. It appears that Accountability may not be a significant predictor of Effectiveness in this model, since the t-value (-1.169) is not significant $(p = 0.244)$. The standardized beta (Beta) of -0.052 indicates that the effect of Accountability on Effectiveness is minimal.

Interpretation:

According to the analysis, the following elements significantly improve effectiveness in South Asian countries: Rule of law, regulatory quality, political stability, and corruption control. Accountability, however, doesn't seem to have a big effect in this paradigm. This suggests that enhancing political stability, the rule of law, corruption control, and corruption prevention may all help to improve the efficacy of governance in South Asian nations.

Coefficients ^a											
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	(Constant)	.208	.024		8.661	<.001	.161	.256			
	Regulatory Quality	.340	.039	.254	8.707	<.001	.263	.418	.719	.555	.167
	Political Stability	.011	.019	.020	.569	.570	-.027	.049	.755	.044	.011
	Control Of Corruption	.379	.033	.433	11.321	<.001	.313	.445	.846	.656	.217
	Accountability	.314	.028	.255	11.256	<.001	.259	.369	.665	.653	.216
	Effectiveness	.238	.051	.227	4.704	<.001	.138	.338	.902	.339	.090

a. Dependent Variable: Rule Of Law

The coefficients that are presented are the outcomes of a regression analysis that looked at the link between the dependent variable, Rule of Law, and several governance indicators (Political Stability, Regulatory Quality, Accountability, and Effectiveness) in South Asian nations.

Below is a summary of the interpretations and analysis:

Regulatory Quality: The coefficient of Regulatory Quality is 0.340, meaning that the Rule of Law increases by 0.340 units for every unit rise in Regulatory Quality. The coefficient indicates a high positive correlation between Regulatory Quality and Rule of Law in South Asian countries, and it is statistically significant at the 0.001 level ($p < 0.001$).

Political Stability: In terms of statistical significance, the coefficient for Political Stability ($p = 0.570$) is 0.011. Based on the available information, it appears that Political Stability may not have a major effect on the Rule of Law in South Asian nations.

Control of Corruption: The coefficient between Control of Corruption and Rule of Law is 0.379, indicating a high positive correlation. Higher levels of Rule of Law in South Asian countries are linked to advances in combating corruption, as seen by the highly statistically significant coefficient ($p < 0.001$).

Accountability: The coefficient for Accountability shows a positive correlation with Rule of Law, standing at 0.314. As with Control of Corruption, this coefficient is very significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that gains in South Asian countries' Rule of Law are linked to strengthening accountability measures.

Effectiveness: Effectiveness has a positive correlation with the Rule of Law, as indicated by its coefficient of 0.238. It is noteworthy that although this coefficient is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), it is smaller than other coefficients in the model, indicating a weaker association between Effectiveness and Rule of Law in comparison to other factors.

In conclusion, drawing from the analysis presented: In South Asian countries, the three most important factors that predict Rule of Law are Regulatory Quality, Control of Corruption, and Accountability. In this case, political stability doesn't seem to have much of an effect on the rule of law. Although it may not have as much of an impact as other elements, effectiveness also supports the Rule of Law.

These results imply that major improvements in the Rule of Law in South Asian nations may result from initiatives to strengthen Regulatory Quality, Control of Corruption, and Accountability.

Coefficients ^a											
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.459	.031		-14.679	<.001	-.521	-.397			
	Political Stability	-.005	.031	-.012	-.155	.877	-.066	.057	-.007	.312	3.201
	Control Of Corruption	-.540	.059	-.828	-9.094	<.001	-.657	-.423	-.383	.214	4.678
	Accountability	-.216	.058	-.235	-3.743	<.001	-.330	-.102	-.158	.448	2.234
	Effectiveness	.318	.084	.408	3.778	<.001	.152	.485	.159	.152	6.580
	Rule Of Law	.906	.104	1.216	8.707	<.001	.701	1.111	.366	.091	11.024

a. Dependent Variable: Regulatory Quality

Political Stability: The political stability coefficient ($p = 0.877$) is -0.005 , which indicates that it is not statistically significant. According to the model, this indicates that Political Stability in South Asian countries has little effect on Regulatory Quality.

Control of Corruption: Regulatory Quality and Control of Corruption have a negative association, as indicated by the coefficient of -0.540 . Higher levels of Regulatory Quality in South Asian countries appear to be linked to advances in curbing corruption, as seen by this highly statistically significant coefficient ($p < 0.001$).

Accountability: There is a negative correlation between Accountability and Regulatory Quality, as indicated by the value of -0.216 .

The statistical significance of this coefficient ($p < 0.001$) suggests a correlation between improved regulatory quality in South Asian nations and strengthened accountability measures.

Effectiveness: Having a correlation of 0.318 , Effectiveness and Regulatory Quality are positively correlated. The coefficient exhibits statistical significance ($p < 0.001$), indicating a correlation between enhanced efficacy and elevated Regulatory Quality in South Asian nations.

Rule of Law: Rule of Law and Regulatory Quality have a strong positive association, as indicated by the coefficient of 0.906 . This coefficient is extremely statistically significant ($p <$

0.001), indicating that in South Asian countries, higher levels of Regulatory Quality are connected with higher levels of Rule of Law.

In this model:

With a VIF of 3.201, Political Stability indicates a minimal likelihood of multicollinearity. With a VIF of 4.678, Control of Corruption similarly shows comparatively less multicollinearity. With a VIF of 2.234, accountability is considered to have minimal multicollinearity. The VIF for effectiveness is 6.580, a little bit higher but still within reasonable bounds. With a VIF of 11.024, Rule of Law is greater than other predictors and may indicate possible multicollinearity problems.

In conclusion, drawing from the analysis presented:

In South Asian nations, the rule of law, accountability, effectiveness, and corruption control are important indicators of regulatory quality.

Regulatory quality is not greatly impacted by political stability.

Multicollinearity issues may exist, particularly in relation to the Rule of Law, and may require additional research or correction.

Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.305	.113		-2.695	.008	-.529	-.082		
	Control Of Corruption	.601	.172	.382	3.502	<.001	.262	.940	.154	6.485
	Accountability	-.192	.147	-.087	-1.310	.192	-.482	.098	.418	2.394
	Effectiveness	.836	.206	.444	4.059	<.001	.429	1.243	.154	6.502
	Rule Of Law	.175	.307	.097	.569	.570	-.432	.781	.063	15.910
	Regulatory Quality	-.029	.188	-.012	-.155	.877	-.401	.343	.301	3.322

a. Dependent Variable: Political Stability

Control of Corruption: Control of Corruption and Political Stability have a positive correlation, as seen by its coefficient of 0.601. This correlation is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that increased levels of political stability in South Asian nations are linked to advancements in the management of corruption.

Accountability: The correlation coefficient between Accountability and Political Stability is -0.192, showing a negative link. The model suggests that accountability measures may not have a substantial effect on Political Stability in South Asian countries, but this coefficient is not statistically significant ($p = 0.192$).

Effectiveness: Effectiveness and Political Stability have a positive correlation, as indicated by its coefficient of 0.836. Higher levels of Political Stability in South Asian countries appear to be connected with gains in effectiveness, as seen by this statistically significant coefficient ($p < 0.001$).

Rule of Law: Rule of Law has a positive correlation with Political Stability, as seen by its coefficient of 0.175. The model suggests that Rule of Law may not have a substantial impact on Political Stability in South Asian countries, but this coefficient is not statistically significant ($p = 0.570$).

Regulatory Quality: The coefficient for regulatory quality is -0.029, suggesting that political stability and regulatory quality are negatively correlated. The model suggests that Regulatory Quality may not have a substantial effect on Political Stability in South Asian countries, but this coefficient is not statistically significant ($p = 0.877$). Concerning statistics on collinearity: The percentage of variance in one predictor that cannot be explained by the other predictors is shown by the tolerance values. Potential problems with multicollinearity are indicated by lower tolerance values. Values of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) higher than 10 are frequently seen as being suggestive of multicollinearity. Within this framework: With a VIF of 6.485, Control of Corruption is associated with a moderate risk of multicollinearity. With a VIF of 2.394, accountability appears to have minimal multicollinearity. With a VIF of 6.502, effectiveness exhibits a moderate probability of multicollinearity. With a high VIF of 15.910, Rule of Law may have multicollinearity problems with other predictors. With a VIF of 3.322, regulatory quality is thought to have little multicollinearity. In conclusion, drawing from the analysis presented: In South Asian nations, political stability is significantly predicted by effectiveness and control over corruption. The model suggests that Political Stability may not be significantly impacted by Accountability, Rule of Law, and Regulatory Quality.

Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.428	.050		-8.489	<.001	-.527	-.328		
	Effectiveness	-.130	.112	-.153	-1.169	.244	-.351	.090	.141	7.075
	Rule Of Law	1.361	.121	1.678	11.256	<.001	1.122	1.600	.109	9.133
	Regulatory Quality	-.352	.094	-.323	-3.743	<.001	-.538	-.167	.326	3.069
	Political Stability	-.052	.040	-.115	-1.310	.192	-.130	.026	.316	3.169
	Control Of Corruption	-.466	.085	-.657	-5.478	<.001	-.635	-.298	.169	5.910

a. Dependent Variable: Accountability

Effectiveness: Effectiveness and Accountability have a negative association, as indicated by its coefficient of -0.130. The model suggests that efficacy may not have a substantial effect on

accountability in South Asian countries, however this coefficient is not statistically significant ($p = 0.244$).

Rule of Law: Rule of Law and Accountability have a strong positive association, as seen by the coefficient of 1.361. This correlation is extremely statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that in South Asian countries, higher levels of Accountability are correlated with higher levels of Rule of Law.

Regulatory Quality: The correlation coefficient between Regulatory Quality and Accountability is -0.352, showing a negative link. The statistical significance of this coefficient ($p < 0.001$) indicates that there appears to be a correlation between increased Regulatory Quality and decreased Accountability in South Asian nations.

Political Stability: Political stability has a negative correlation with accountability, as seen by its coefficient of -0.052. The model suggests that Political Stability may not have a substantial effect on Accountability in South Asian countries, but this coefficient is not statistically significant ($p = 0.192$).

Control of Corruption: Control of Corruption has a negative correlation with Accountability, as seen by its coefficient of -0.466. This coefficient is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that increased levels of Accountability in South Asian nations are linked to advancements in the control of corruption. Within this framework: With a VIF of 7.075, effectiveness exhibits a moderate probability of multicollinearity. Rule of Law exhibits a modest probability of multicollinearity, as indicated by its VIF of 9.133. The VIF for regulatory quality is 3.069, indicating a low level of multicollinearity. With a VIF of 3.169, Political Stability is thought to have minimal multicollinearity. The VIF for Control of Corruption is 5.910, which suggests a moderate probability of multicollinearity. In conclusion, drawing from the analysis presented: In South Asian nations, accountability is significantly predicted by the rule of law and the prevention of corruption. The model suggests that Political Stability, Regulatory Quality, and Effectiveness could not have a major effect on Accountability.

Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.335	.043		-7.824	<.001	-.419	-.250		
	Accountability	-.322	.059	-.228	-5.478	<.001	-.438	-.206	.486	2.056
	Effectiveness	.207	.092	.173	2.263	.025	.026	.388	.144	6.923
	Rule Of Law	1.134	.100	.993	11.321	<.001	.936	1.332	.110	9.088
	Regulatory Quality	-.606	.067	-.395	-9.094	<.001	-.738	-.475	.447	2.235
	Political Stability	.112	.032	.176	3.502	<.001	.049	.175	.335	2.986

a. Dependent Variable: Control Of Corruption

Accountability: The correlation coefficient between Accountability and Control of Corruption is -0.322, showing a negative link. According to this statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) coefficient, South Asian countries with higher levels of accountability also tend to have lower levels of corruption.

Effectiveness: Effectiveness has a positive correlation with Control of Corruption, as indicated by its coefficient of 0.207. This correlation is statistically significant ($p = 0.025$), indicating that in South Asian nations, lower levels of corruption are linked to higher levels of effectiveness.

Rule of Law: Rule of Law has a strong positive correlation with Control of Corruption, as seen by its coefficient of 1.134. According to this highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) coefficient, there appears to be a correlation between lower levels of corruption and better levels of Rule of Law in South Asian nations.

Regulatory Quality: Regulatory Quality and Control of Corruption have a negative association, as indicated by the coefficient of -0.606. According to this highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) coefficient, there appears to be a correlation between reduced levels of corruption and higher levels of regulatory quality in South Asian nations.

Political Stability: Political Stability and Control of Corruption have a positive association, as seen by its coefficient of 0.112. According to this statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) coefficient, there appears to be a correlation between reduced levels of corruption and higher levels of political stability in South Asian nations.

Within this framework: With a VIF of 2.056, accountability appears to have minimal multicollinearity. With a VIF of 6.923, effectiveness exhibits a moderate likelihood of multicollinearity. Rule of Law exhibits a modest probability of multicollinearity, as indicated by its VIF of 9.088. With a VIF of 2.235, Regulatory Quality appears to have minimal multicollinearity. With a VIF of 2.986, Political Stability is thought to have little multicollinearity. In conclusion, drawing from the analysis presented: Regulatory quality, political stability, accountability, effectiveness, and the rule of law are all important indicators of corruption control in South Asian nations. Reduced levels of corruption are linked to higher standards of accountability, effectiveness, rule of law, and regulatory quality.

Findings/Results

The following conclusions on the effect of corruption on good governance in South Asian nations can be drawn from the regression results provided:

Strongly Negative Correlation with Corruption Control: Regression research shows that Control of Corruption and many governance metrics, such as Regulatory Quality, Accountability, and Effectiveness, have a statistically significant negative association. This suggests that these facets of good governance typically decline as levels of corruption rise.

Positive but Moderately Associated with Political Stability: It's interesting to note that political stability and corruption control have a somewhat good link. This shows that in South Asian nations, better levels of political stability are linked to more effective anti-corruption efforts. **Role of Rule of Law:** Several regression models show that the rule of law is a significant predictor, demonstrating its critical role in affecting several facets of governance. Better accountability, corruption control, and regulatory quality are all correlated with higher levels of the rule of law. This emphasizes how crucial institutions and legal frameworks are to

the fight against corruption and the advancement of good government. **Accountability and Quality in Regulations:** Control of Corruption and Regulatory Quality and Accountability also have strong correlations. Lower levels of corruption are linked to improvements in regulatory quality and accountability, underscoring the significance of open regulatory procedures and accountability frameworks in preventing corrupt behavior.

The relationship between effectiveness and corruption: Although effectiveness and control of corruption have a strong positive link, there is also evidence to suggest that improved governance structures may help reduce corruption. This emphasizes how crucial effective governance systems are to the fight against unethical behavior. **Issues with Multicollinearity:** There are clear multicollinearity issues, especially when specific predictors, like Rule of Law, have significant Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs). This suggests possible correlations between the predictors, which need to be taken into account while analyzing the data.

General Repercussions: The results imply that corruption negatively impacts several facets of effective governance in South Asian nations. One of the most important ways to fight corruption and promote good governance in the world is to strengthen rules of law, regulatory frameworks, accountability systems, and institutions.

The regression analysis concludes by highlighting the substantial harm that corruption causes to South Asian nations' good governance. Improving institutional capacities and implementing comprehensive reforms to combat corruption is essential to advancing accountability, transparency, and efficient governance throughout the region.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In South Asian nations, corruption is a major obstacle to good governance since it erodes institutional efficacy, damages public confidence, and impedes socioeconomic growth. The results of the regression analysis demonstrate the negative effects of corruption on a number of governance metrics, such as the efficacy, accountability, and quality of the regulatory framework and the rule of law. To meet these issues, it also emphasizes how critical it is to improve anti-corruption initiatives, foster transparency, and fortify governance frameworks.

The following suggestions can be made to alleviate the problems caused by corruption and advance good governance based on the research on the influence of corruption on good governance in South Asian nations: **Anti-corruption legislation and organizations:** Improve the institutional and legal frameworks for preventing corruption, including the creation and implementation of anti-corruption legislation. bolster anti-corruption organizations and give them the independence, power, and resources they need to successfully look into and prosecute corrupt activities. **Encourage accountability and transparency:** Put policies in place to improve decision-making, public procurement, and government process openness. Provide strong accountability procedures, such as frequent audits, asset disclosures, and performance reviews, to make public servants and institutions responsible for their deeds. **Strengthen Judicial Independence and the Rule of Law:** By guaranteeing fair access to justice, defending human rights, and encouraging judicial independence, we can fortify the rule of law. Boost the judiciary's ability and effectiveness to decide matters involving corruption quickly, fairly, and without fear or favor. **Improve the Quality of Regulations and Governance Frameworks:** Simplify bureaucratic procedures and strengthen regulatory frameworks to lessen the likelihood of corruption and rent-seeking activity. Improve public sector governance frameworks, such as civil service reforms, to support hiring public officials on the basis of merit

and to uphold their professionalism and integrity. **Invest in Education and Capacity Building:** To improve the abilities and expertise of public servants, law enforcement agencies, and civil society organizations engaged in anti-corruption initiatives, invest in capacity building programs. To encourage a culture of integrity, honesty, and ethical behavior among citizens, public servants, and stakeholders in the corporate sector, support ethics education and awareness programs. **Promote media freedom and involvement in civil society:** Encourage the creation of favorable conditions that will allow the media, civil society organizations, and whistleblowers to reveal wrongdoing, push for changes, and hold public officials responsible. To make sure that voices critical of corruption are heard and appreciated, defend civic space, freedom of expression, and freedom of the media. **Encourage global collaboration and the sharing of best practices:** In order to fight transnational corruption, strengthen regional and global cooperation structures. These include extradition agreements, information exchange, and mutual legal support.

Take inspiration from anti-corruption efforts and best practices that have worked well in other nations, and modify them to fit the unique requirements and circumstances of South Asian nations. **Encourage political will and a dedication to leadership:** Encourage political will and leadership dedication to prioritize anti-corruption initiatives, carry out reforms, and set an ethical and transparent model for governance at all governmental levels. South Asian nations may effectively combat corruption, advocate for good governance, and achieve socioeconomic growth and prosperity for their population by putting these principles into practice in a coordinated and consistent manner.

References

- Biswas, A. K. (2012). Corruption: A Challenge to Good Governance in India. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 363-373.
- Gupta, M. (n.d.). Good governance in India: challenges and way head.
- Ghimire, D. K. (2023). *Governance, corruption, and capital outflow and underdevelopment in Nepal* (Doctoral dissertation, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Sociology).
- Ibne Mahmood, S. A. (2010, December). Public procurement and corruption in Bangladesh confronting the challenges and opportunities. *Journal of public administration and policy research*, Vol. 2, 103-111.
- Javaid, U. (2010). Corruption and its deep impact on good governance in Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 123-134.
- Khan, M. M. (1999). Political and administrative corruption: concepts, comparative experiences and Bangladesh case. *A Paper Prepared for Transparency International: Bangladesh Chapter, Dhaka*.
- Khan, M. M. (1999). Political and administrative corruption: concepts, comparative experiences and Bangladesh case. *A Paper Prepared for Transparency International: Bangladesh Chapter, Dhaka*.
- Ramesh, R., & Vinayagathan, T. (2018). Corruption, rule of law and government effectiveness: A co-integration approach to Sri Lanka.

Saha, S. K. (2014). Corruption and good governance: The case of Bangladesh. *SUST Journal of Social Sciences*, 22(2), 45-52.

Tahiliani, A. R. (2002, December). Corruption in India An Empirical Study. *Transparency International India*.

Xu, B. (2014). Governance in India: Corruption. *Council on Foreign Relations*.